

Original Research

The Influence of Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital on Green Banking Within Regional Banks in Indonesia

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the assessment of bank health levels using the Risk-Based Bank Rating (RBBR) method, which includes Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital in relation to the implementation of green banking practices. This research was conducted on regional banks that are members of financial services authority (OJK) in Indonesia, totaling 27 companies that met the sample criteria. The research period is 4 years from 2020 to 2023, resulting in a total of 108 research samples. This study uses a Common Effect Model to test the hypothesis. The research results show that risk profile and earnings have a significant negative effect on the green banking. Meanwhile, good corporate governance does not have a significant effect on the green banking. Capitalization has a significant positive effect on the green banking. The study contributes to green banking literature by showing that external regulatory and stakeholder pressures are more influential than corporate governance in promoting green banking. It underscores capitalization as a key enabler and identifies profit orientation and risk aversion as barriers, highlighting the need for stronger institutional frameworks.

Keywords: Capital, earnings, good corporate governance, green banking risk profile.

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Introduction

Banking is an economic sub-sector that facilitates operations and the execution of development, functioning as a mechanism to achieve the objectives of national development. Currently, in conjunction with the growing global focus on environmental concerns, the banking sector is seeing a transition in its practices and operations. The notion of a green economy, which fundamentally advocates for the reduction of environmental effect in all economic activities, is also embraced by the banking sector. One method is via the concept of Green Banking (Kurniawan, 2021). The notion of Green Banking refers to a banking initiative aimed at prioritizing sustainability in credit allocation and operating practices. Banks are not immediately classified as major contributors to environmental pollution. The banking sector is not free from the problem of escalating environmental degradation (Alfiah & Pujati, 2024). Green banking has gained global significance as countries increasingly prioritize environmental sustainability alongside economic growth. By promoting eco-friendly practices and financing green projects, banks play a crucial role in supporting sustainable financial development. From Europe to Asia, green banking initiatives are helping economies transition toward low-carbon, resilient futures while ensuring long-term financial stability (Sarraf, Mikrad, & Sunanto, 2022).

The implementation of Green Banking practices through regulations commenced with the issuance of Bank Indonesia Regulation (PBI) Number 14/15/PBI/2012, which pertains to the Evaluation of General Bank Asset Quality. Article 11, letter e, mandates an environmental assessment by debtors as part of credit prerequisites, which may manifest as an Environmental Impact Assessment (AMDAL). Subsequent to the formation of OJK, it promulgated POJK Number 51/POJK.03 of 2017 regarding the Implementation of Sustainable Finance for Financial Services Institutions, Issuers, and Public Companies. The modification of PBI Number 14/15/PBI of 2012 regarding the Evaluation of General Bank Asset Quality to POJK Number 51/POJK.03 of 2017 undoubtedly entails legal ramifications for both banking and non-banking Financial Services Institutions, specifically the requirement to adopt sustainable finance in their operational activities (Naiborhu, 2023).

Figure 1. Banks that have implemented Green Banking as of April 2022
Source: (Katadata Insight Center, 2022)

According to the Katadata Insight Center (KIC) report titled "Survey on Public Perception of Sustainable Financial Products" during the period from March 28 to April 4, 2022, there are currently only four banks that are widely perceived to have implemented green banking principles. In the first position is a private bank, namely Bank Central Asia (BCA), which is considered to have implemented green banking by 25.7% of respondents. After that, there are three state-owned banks, namely Bank Rakyat Indonesia (BRI) with a percentage of 23.7%, Bank Negara Indonesia (BNI) 12.6%, and Bank Mandiri 12.1%. Meanwhile, other banks are not perceived as green banking practitioners, with each percentage below 2% (Katadata Insight Center, 2022). Therefore, further research is needed at this time to determine whether regional banks still do not implement green banking much or have actually started to adopt the concept of green banking. For example, the Sumsel Babel Regional Development Bank has started moving towards green banking in 2023 because it considers green banking important for emphasizing net zero emissions to be achieved by 2060 (www.topbusiness.id, 2023). This indicates that regional banks are beginning to pay attention to the concept of green banking just like other general banks.

Through the management of social and environmental risks, regional banks are expected to be able to compete and survive in conducting their financial business. The implementation of green banking aims to reduce social inequality, prevent environmental damage, preserve biodiversity, and promote the efficient use of energy and natural resources (Handajani, Rifai, & Husnan, 2019). The growing urgency of climate change and environmental degradation has intensified pressure on the banking sector to adopt sustainable and responsible practices. Green banking, which integrates environmental considerations into banking operations and lending decisions, has become a focal point in aligning the financial system with global sustainability goals. While existing studies predominantly emphasize large national or multinational banks, this research turns its attention to regional banks, offering a novel and significant contribution to the field.

Regional banks, often embedded deeply within local economies, play a critical role in financing small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and community-based projects. Their decisions have direct implications for localized environmental outcomes, yet they operate under distinct structural, regulatory, and resource constraints compared to their national counterparts. Focusing on regional banks fills a critical gap in the literature by uncovering how these institutions respond to external pressures, such as regulatory mandates and stakeholder expectations, within more limited operational and capital frameworks.

The implementation of green banking cannot be carried out without considering the factors that influence it. One of these factors is the bank's health level (Purwadani & Imronuddin, 2023). The level of bank health is the result of an assessment of the bank's condition conducted on the bank's risks and performance. Bank Indonesia Regulation 13/1/PBI/2011 Article 2 states that banks are required to maintain and/or improve the Bank's Health Level by applying the principles of prudence and risk management in conducting business activities. The health of the bank must be maintained and/or improved so that public trust in the bank can be preserved (Sitorus, et al., 2023). Therefore, Bank Indonesia and the Financial Services Authority have taken strategic steps to encourage the implementation of risk management as outlined in Bank Indonesia Regulation (PBI) Number 13/1/PBI/2011 and Financial Services Authority Regulation

(POJK) Number 4/POJK.03/2016 concerning the Assessment of the Health Level of Commercial Banks using the Risk-Based Bank Rating (RBBR) method (Sarra, Mikrad, & Sunanto, 2022).

The Risk-Based Bank Rating (RBBR) method, which is an improvement of the CAMELS method (Capital, Assets, Quality, Management, Earning, Liquidity, and Sensitivity to Market List). The advantage of the RBBR method is that it places greater emphasis on the importance of management quality. Quality management will certainly enhance income factors as well as capital factors both directly and indirectly (Kosim & Pratama, 2021). The Risk-Based Bank Rating (RBBR) method is a policy issued by the Government as a tool for assessing the health level of banks measured by Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital (Purwadani & Imronuddin, 2023). RBBR evaluates banks based on key dimensions such as risk profile, earnings, capitalization, and governance. These factors are not only central to determining financial soundness but are increasingly relevant in assessing a bank's readiness and capacity to implement green banking initiatives.

The assessment of the bank's health level using the Risk-Based Bank Rating (RBBR) method, which includes Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital, is believed to provide an overview of the banking sector's commitment to implementing green banking practices. Thus, by examining the capital structure of banks in Indonesia, not only state-owned/national private banks are required to implement green banking, but also regional development banks (BPD). Both the practice and reporting of green banking are also important for regional banks, as their activities generally prioritize economic improvement in their regions. Therefore, the alignment between the health of these banks in implementing green banking practices is crucial to support the achievement of net zero emissions by 2060. Studies on the implementation of green banking have been conducted in several relevant empirical researches, but this research offers novelty by incorporating Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital as variables influencing green banking within a single research model, particularly using regional banks as the research object. By considering the existing research factors, the research questions of this study are what is the influence of Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital on green banking.

Literature Review

Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy Theory is the most widely used theory to explain environmental and social disclosures. The legitimacy theory has advantages over other theories because it provides disclosure strategies that can be adopted by organizations to legitimize their existence, which can be empirically tested. Therefore, companies are increasingly aware that the sustainability of the company also depends on the good relationship between the company and the environment and society in which the company operates (Kurniawan, 2021).

The legitimacy theory explains that companies will continuously ensure that their operational activities always adhere to the values and norms of the surrounding community. The company will voluntarily report its activities when management

perceives that these activities have met the expectations of the surrounding community (Siregar & Haryono, 2023). Therefore, with a good level of banking health, it is necessary to accompany the legitimacy of the bank to continue improving green banking disclosures so that the expectations of the community are met.

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory is a recognized framework for conducting sustainability report research about environmental and social disclosures. The initial citations of this idea were by Freeman and McVea in 1984, who articulated that stakeholders are entities that exert considerable influence on the success or failure of an organization. Freeman succinctly characterizes stakeholder theory as the manager's reaction to the corporate environment (Siregar & Haryono, 2023). To tackle sustainability challenges, banks can adopt and promote green banking, ensuring their business activities conform to ethical standards within the financial sector (Petro, Octavia, & Diarsyad, 2023). To improve the company's reputation, it is essential to adopt green banking practices as a corporate responsibility for environmental preservation, which will influence future outcomes. This initiative by banking institutions aims to cultivate stakeholder trust through the adoption of green banking practices, reflecting their commitment to environmental conservation (Setyoko & Wijayanti, 2022).

Green banking is a reaction to stakeholder demands for banking institutions to operate more ethically. The viability of banks will be contingent upon the significant influence of their stakeholders, particularly regarding the efficacy of green banking initiatives (Handajani, Rifai, & Husnan, 2019). Consequently, effective corporate governance is essential for facilitating the execution of green banking initiatives. Effective corporate governance serves as a framework to address the interests of stakeholders. The interests of all stakeholders must be equitably distributed (Ahmar, Al Rahmah, & Darminto, 2024).

Resource-Based View Theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) asserts that a firm's internal resources—such as risk management systems, governance frameworks, earnings generation, and capital adequacy—are essential assets that can foster enduring competitive advantage (Kurniawan, 2021). Within the realm of regional banking, the Resource-Based View (RBV) posits that banks possessing resilient risk profiles, elevated levels of good corporate governance (GCG), substantial earnings, and powerful capital buffers are strategically poised to effectively adopt green banking practices. This indicates that regional banks that proficiently manage credit and operational risks, comply with governance best practices, achieve robust profits, and sustain sufficient capital are not only more resilient but also better positioned to finance sustainable, eco-friendly projects—reinforcing the RBV principle that internal capabilities are essential for both competitive advantage and green innovation.

Previous Research Results

The evaluation of risk profile components comprises eight categories of risk: credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk, operational risk, legal risk, strategic risk, compliance risk,

and reputational risk. Among these risks, only two can be quantified using financial ratios: credit risk and liquidity risk (Simatupang, Tobing, & Banjarnahor, 2024). The research exclusively examines credit risk, which pertains to the primary banking function of credit management (Sarrah, Mikrad, & Sunanto, 2022). The Non-Performing Loan (NPL) ratio serves as a metric for assessing credit risk. A larger NPL correlates with diminished transparency in green banking disclosures. When banks encounter elevated non-performing loans (NPLs), their primary focus is to resolve the problem of non-performing loans and enhance asset quality. In the face of financial difficulties, banks may prioritize restoring their financial stability above investing in green banking projects (Ahmar, Al Rahmah, & Darminto, 2024). Consistent with the findings of Citraningtyas, Widagdo, & Ika (2024), which identified a correlation between the NPL ratio and green banking disclosure, Furqan & Sutrisno (2024) showed no correlation between NPL and green credit, a key indication of green banking disclosure.

The assessment of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) factors is an evaluation of the bank's management regarding the implementation of GCG principles. GCG serves as a guideline for stakeholder agreements in identifying and formulating strategic decisions effectively and in a coordinated manner (Simatupang, Tobing, & Banjarnahor, 2024). Therefore, the size of the board of commissioners becomes one of the important indicators of the implementation of GCG principles because it is considered one of the parties responsible for the company's decision-making (Petro, Octavia, & Diarsyad, 2023). In facing the various interests of stakeholders, banking companies require corporate governance to ensure the equality of interests among stakeholders so that the business and managerial decisions made do not harm the interests of any one stakeholder, including the demand for financial institutions to conduct ethical business practices such as disclosing green banking to external parties. Therefore, the larger the size of the board of commissioners, the greater the increase in green banking disclosure (Ahmar, Al Rahmah, & Darminto, 2024). This is in line with the findings of Handajani (2019) and Cupian, Mulyana, & Noven (2023) who found the influence of board size on green banking. Meanwhile, Citraningtyas, Widagdo, & Ika (2024) did not find an influence of the board of commissioners' size on green banking.

The assessment of the profitability factor (earnings) is the bank's ability to increase its profits, whether in each period or to measure the level of operational efficiency and profitability achieved by the concerned bank (Simatupang, Tobing, & Banjarnahor, 2024). The profitability factor can be measured with two ratios, namely Return On Asset (ROA) and Net Interest Margin (NIM). However, this study focuses only on the ROA ratio indicator because this ratio is used by bank management to measure success in generating profits from the use of all its resources or assets. A high ROA ratio will motivate management to always report their best performance in an effort to attract investor interest. One form of performance reporting is by reporting the green banking activities that have been carried out (Kurniawan, 2021). This is in line with the research findings of Rachmawati, Karim, & Manan (2023) which found the influence of ROA on green banking. Meanwhile, (Ahmar, Al Rahmah, & Darminto, 2024) did not find any influence of ROA on green banking.

The assessment of capital factors includes the level of capital adequacy, including that related to the bank's risk profile and capital management, which can be measured using

the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), a ratio used as a measure of the bank's ability to provide the minimum capital required for managing the bank's assets (Simatupang, Tobing, & Banjarnahor, 2024). One of the challenges for banks in implementing green banking programs is the high capital costs required. This will be useful for promotion costs, training, and managerial expenses. CAR becomes a key variable for banks to develop the implementation of green banking, such as training costs, promotion costs, and managerial expenses. The higher the CAR a bank possesses, it can be assumed that the bank can manage green banking well (Furqan & Sutrisno, 2024). In line with the research findings of Citraningtyas, Widagdo, & Ika (2024) which found the influence of CAR on green banking. Meanwhile, Siregar & Haryono (2023) did not find any influence of CAR on green banking.

Hypothesis Development

Risk Profile on Green Banking

In an effort to address sustainability issues, banks can respond by implementing and promoting green banking so that their business practices align with ethical business practices in the banking financial industry itself (Petro, Octavia, & Diarsyad, 2023). The legitimacy theory explains that companies will continuously ensure that their operational activities always adhere to the values and norms of the surrounding community (Siregar & Haryono, 2023). Additionally, Stakeholder Theory emphasizes that banks must address the interests of multiple stakeholders by transparently reporting their environmental impact and sustainable finance initiatives. When the risk profile is in a good position, it sends a positive signal to the market, potentially influencing stock prices (Titman, Keown, & Martin, 2018). Furthermore, based on the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory, internal resources like sound risk management, capital strength, and good governance serve as strategic assets that enable banks to implement and sustain green banking effectively. Thus, it is expected that the signal will influence the initiation of green banking practices. This is supported by the research findings of Citraningtyas, Widagdo, & Ika (2024), which found an influence of the NPL ratio as a proxy for risk profile on the disclosure of green banking.

H₁: Risk profile negatively impacts the green banking.

Good Corporate Governance on Green Banking

The good level of banking health, it needs to be accompanied by the legitimacy of the bank to continue improving green banking disclosure so that public expectations are met. According to Legitimacy Theory, organizations seek to align their operations with societal norms and values to maintain their acceptance and reputation. Green banking is a response to pressure from stakeholders so that banking companies can conduct their practices more ethically. The existence of banks will be determined by the crucial role of their stakeholders, including in the success of green banking practices (Handajani, Rifai, & Husnan, 2019). Therefore, good corporate governance is necessary to influence the implementation of green banking. This reflects the principles of Stakeholder Theory, which asserts that meeting the expectations of all stakeholders is crucial for long-term success. Moreover, based on the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory, internal organizational capabilities such

as a competent board structure, transparent governance, and sound risk management are valuable resources that can give banks a competitive edge in adopting and sustaining green banking practices. The larger the size of the board of commissioners, the greater the disclosure of green banking as a form of stakeholder responsibility to the community (Ahmar, Al Rahmah, & Darminto, 2024). This is in line with the findings of (Handajani, Rifai, & Husnan, 2019) and Cupian, Mulyana, & Noven (2023), who found the influence of board size on green banking.

H₂: Good corporate governance positively impacts the green banking.

Earnings on Green Banking

A good level of banking health needs to be accompanied by the legitimacy of the bank to continue enhancing green banking disclosures so that public expectations are met. According to Legitimacy Theory, banks seek to align their actions with societal values and norms to maintain public trust and social approval, especially as environmental concerns become more prominent (Sarra, Mikrad, & Sunanto, 2022). The assessment of the profitability (earnings) factor is the bank's ability to increase its profits, whether in each period or to measure the level of operational efficiency and profitability achieved by the respective bank (Simatupang, Tobing, & Banjarnahor, 2024). Profitability (earnings) which is proxied by the Return on Asset (ROA) ratio, when at a high position, will motivate management to always report their best performance in an effort to provide positive signals to investors. Thus, the initiation of green banking practices will also increase as a manifestation of the Company's good performance (Kurniawan, 2021). This aligns with Stakeholder Theory, which suggests that companies, including banks, must fulfill the expectations of a wide range of stakeholders by adopting ethical, transparent, and environmentally conscious practices. Additionally, the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory supports the idea that internal capabilities such as financial strength, operational efficiency, and strategic management are critical resources that enable banks to implement and sustain green banking initiatives. This is supported by the research findings of Rachmawati, Karim, & Manan (2023) which found the influence of ROA on green banking.

H₃: Earnings positively impact the green banking.

Capital on Green Banking

The assessment of capital factors includes the level of capital adequacy, including that related to the bank's risk profile and capital management, which can be measured using the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) (Simatupang, Tobing, & Banjarnahor, 2024). One of the challenges for banks in implementing green banking programs is the high capital costs required. According to the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory, capital strength is a strategic internal resource that can provide a competitive advantage are better equipped to allocate funds for long-term, sustainability-oriented projects, including green banking. From the lens of Legitimacy Theory, adequate capital also supports the bank's ability to meet societal expectations, including environmental responsibility, thereby helping the institution maintain its legitimacy in the eyes of stakeholders and the public. Furthermore, based on Stakeholder Theory, strong capital positions allow banks to fulfill their

obligations by supporting sustainable financing and increasing transparency. The higher the CAR a bank possesses, the more it can be assumed that the bank can manage green banking effectively (Furqan & Sutrisno, 2024). In line with the research findings of Citraningtyas, Widagdo, & Ika (2024) which found the influence of CAR on green banking.

H4: Capital positively impacts the green banking.

Methodology

Research type and approach

The type of research used is quantitative. The type of data in this research is documentary data in the form of annual banking reports and sustainability reports from banks that are members of financial services authority (OJK), obtained by downloading data from the respective Regional Bank websites from the year 2020 - 2023. This method was chosen to statistically show and describe the relationship between the health level of banks (Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital) and green banking practices.

Operational Variables

The operational variables of the research model is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Variable Definitions and Operations

Variables	Definition	Indicator
Green Banking (Y)	Green banking is a financial institution that prioritizes sustainability in its business practices, where this understanding of green banking is based on four elements of life: nature, well-being, economy, and society (Alfiah & Pujiati, 2024).	The Green Banking Disclosure Index (GBDI) indicator developed by Bose et al. (2018) consisting of 21 items.
Risk Profile (X1)	The assessment of risk profile factors consists of eight risks, namely: credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk, operational risk, legal risk, strategic risk, compliance risk, and reputational risk (Simatupang, Tobing, & Banjarnahor, 2024).	$NPL = \frac{\text{Non-Performing Loan}}{\text{Total Loan}} \times 100\%$ (Kosim & Pratama, 2021)
Good Corporate Governance (X2)	Good corporate governance serves as a guideline for stakeholder agreements in identifying and formulating strategic decisions effectively and in a coordinated manner (Simatupang, Tobing, & Banjarnahor, 2024).	Total number of the board of commissioners (Citraningtyas, Widagdo, & Ika, 2024)

Variables	Definition	Indicator
Earnings (X3)	The assessment of the profitability factor (earnings) is the bank's ability to increase its profits, whether in each period or to measure the level of operational efficiency and profitability achieved by the respective bank (Simatupang, Tobing, & Banjarnahor, 2024).	ROA = Net Income/Total Assets x 100% (Sarraf, Mikrad, & Sunanto, 2022)
Capital (X4)	The assessment of capital factors includes the adequacy of capital, including that related to the bank's risk profile and capital management (Simatupang, Tobing, & Banjarnahor, 2024).	CAR = Capital/Risk Weighted Assets x 100% (Sarraf, Mikrad, & Sunanto, 2022)

Population and Sample

The population in this study consists of Regional Banks in Indonesia that are members of financial services authority (OJK), totaling 27 Regional Banks. Specifically, the researcher chose to use the census sampling technique, which is use of the entire population as a research sample. The final sample for this research comprises 27 regional banks over a 4-year period, yielding a total of 108 observational data points.

Data Analysis Technique

Statistical test using panel data estimation method. The panel data estimation method offers several key advantages that make it valuable in empirical research, especially in fields like finance, economics, and environmental policy. By combining cross-sectional and time-series data, panel data allows researchers to control for unobserved heterogeneity—individual-specific factors that do not change over time but could bias results if omitted. This method also increases the number of observations, improving statistical power and efficiency of estimates. Additionally, panel data captures dynamic changes over time, making it well-suited for analyzing the evolution of variables such as risk profiles, good corporate governance, earnings, capital, and green banking practices. It can also detect effects that purely cross-sectional or time-series data might miss. The development of panel data models is the result of contributions from several leading economists and econometricians. Key figures include Zvi Griliches, Jerry Hausman, and Cheng Hsiao, who advanced the theoretical and practical applications of panel data. Common models such as Fixed Effects (FE) and Random Effects (RE) are widely used, with further advancements by researchers like Badi H. Baltagi and Jeffrey M. Wooldridge.

The regression model can be formulated in the following equation:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Using panel data, we generate different intercept and slope coefficients for each object and time period. There are several methods that can be used to estimate the panel data

regression model, namely the approach Common Effects, Fixed Effects, and Random Effects. Tests will be carried out using the eViews software. To choose the best model, it can be done with three tests, namely chow test, Hausman test, and Lagrange Multiplier test. For robustness test, we added several control variables such as company size (C1), leverage (C2), and company age (C3). Company size, leverage, and company age are included as control variables because they represent firm-specific characteristics that may influence the extent of green banking disclosures and implementation. Larger banks typically have more resources, higher public visibility, and greater pressure from stakeholders to adopt sustainable practices. They are also more likely to have the infrastructure and institutional capacity to support green banking initiatives. Therefore, company size can affect a bank's ability and willingness to engage in environmental disclosure and green finance. Leverage reflects the proportion of a company's debt relative to its equity. Highly leveraged banks may be more risk-averse and less likely to invest in long-term, high-cost sustainability initiatives due to financial constraints. Older banks may have more experience, established reputations, and developed governance structures that can either encourage or hinder innovation in green banking. Long-standing institutions might be more conservative but may also feel stronger pressure to maintain legitimacy through environmental and social responsibility.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

The Table 2 represents the descriptive statistics for all variables.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the study

No	Description	X1	X2	X3	X4	Y
1	Mean	2.120370	2.203704	2.042500	25.89898	48.98519
2	Median	2.000000	2.000000	2.020000	24.59500	52.38000
3	Maximum	4.000000	4.000000	4.310000	44.72000	71.43000
4	Minimum	2.000000	1.000000	-3.800000	17.31000	9.520000
5	Std. Dev.	0.354348	0.525237	1.140170	5.586049	14.36702
6	Observation	108	108	108	108	108

The study analyzed the green banking disclosure index (GBDI) of regional banking companies from 2020 to 2023, revealing that they disclose green banking information for 48.98519% of available disclosure items. The risk profile of these banks was rated low, with Bank Banten being categorized as high risk. The corporate governance of these banks was rated well, with Bank Banten achieving the highest score for effective corporate governance. The return on asset (ROA) was 2.0425%, indicating that the banks have optimized their asset management. Bank Sulawesi Tenggara had the highest ROA value of 4.31% in 2023, while Bank Banten recorded a minimal ROA value of -3.8% in 2020. The capital adequacy ratio (CAR) was 25.89898%, indicating that the banks possess appropriate capitalization. Bank Banten recorded the highest CAR value of 44.72% in 2023, indicating exceptional capitalization. The study found no data deviation in the CAR variable, as the standard deviation is less than the average value.

Best Model Selection

This study uses model selection analysis to examine panel data regression for data description. The subsequent outcomes of the model selection analysis test are presented.

Table 3. Best Model Selection Test

No.	Test	Hypothesis	Probability	Selected Model
1	Chow	H ₀ : CEM	0.1243	Common Effect Model (CEM)
		H _a : FEM		
	Hausman	H ₀ : REM	0.5622	
		H _a : FEM		
	Lagrange Multiplier	H ₀ : CEM	0.9397	
		H _a : REM		

This study uses the common effect model for its investigation of model selection. The use of the Common Effect Model is methodologically justified based on the homogeneity of the sample, the nature of the explanatory variables, diagnostic testing outcomes, and the objective of estimating general effects across regional banks. The subsequent phase involves the conventional assumption test of the data. The classical assumption test evaluates the quality of the data obtained by the researcher to determine its suitability for use as a reference in the study.

Figure 2. Normality Test

Based on the results above, it can be concluded that the probability value of 0.072512 is greater than 0.05, which means the data is considered normally distributed.

Hypothesis Test

The analysis results for the relationship between the health level of banks (Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, and Capital) and green banking practices are presented in table 4. For robustness test, we added several control variables such as company size (C1), leverage (C2), and company age (C3).

Table 4. Analysis Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-60.38631	8.169878	-7.391336	0.0000
X1	-4.932277	1.451253	-3.398635	0.0010
X2	-1.934232	2.249749	-0.859754	0.3920
X3	-2.151884	0.517798	-4.155839	0.0001
X4	0.308805	0.105271	2.933432	0.0042
C1	1.962042	0.866605	2.264056	0.0257
C2	-0.004118	0.001700	-2.423053	0.0172
C3	22.79220	2.199766	10.36119	0.0000
R-squared	0.169345	Mean dependent var		64.28154
Adjusted R-squared	0.111199	S.D. dependent var		34.68339
S.E. of regression	13.85012	Sum squared resid		19182.57
F-statistic	2.912408	Durbin-Watson stat		1.522913
Prob(F-statistic)	0.008164			

Based on table 6, the adjusted R-Squared value of 0.111199 indicates a coefficient of determination of 11.1199%. This means that the variables of risk profile, good corporate governance, earnings, and capital together can influence the green banking variable by 11.1199%.

The F-statistic probability value of $0.008164 < 0.05$ indicates a simultaneous influence of the risk profile variable, good corporate governance, earnings, and capital together can affect the green banking variable.

The probability value of the risk profile variable is $0.0010 < 0.05$ and the coefficient value is -4.932277, indicating that the risk profile variable has a significant negative effect on the green banking variable. Therefore, the research hypothesis (H1) stating that the Risk Profile has a negative effect on green banking is accepted.

The probability value of the good corporate governance variable is $0.3920 > 0.05$ and the coefficient value is -1.934232, indicating that the good corporate governance variable does not have a significant effect on the green banking variable. Therefore, the research hypothesis (H2) stating that good corporate governance has a positive effect on green banking is rejected.

The probability value of the earnings variable is $0.0001 < 0.05$ and the coefficient value is -2.151884, indicating that the earnings variable has a significant negative effect on the green banking variable. Therefore, the research hypothesis (H3) stating that earnings has a positive effect on green banking is rejected.

The probability value of the capital variable is $0.0042 < 0.05$ and the coefficient value is 0.308805, indicating that the capital variable has a positive and significant partial effect on the green banking variable. Therefore, the research hypothesis (H4) stating that capitalization has a positive and significant effect on green banking is accepted.

Risk Profile and Green Banking

The risk profile negatively affects green banking because the decision to implement green banking practices is more influenced by external factors such as regulations, stakeholder pressure, and corporate reputation strategies, rather than by internal risk preferences. Additionally, many financial institutions have not fully integrated environmental risks into conventional risk assessments, so the risk profile does not become the main determinant in the implementation of green banking.

According to Legitimacy Theory, banks may implement green banking practices largely to preserve or augment their social legitimacy among regulators, customers, investors, and the general public. In this setting, green efforts act as a strategic response to increasing public expectations and regulatory oversight, rather than reflecting internal risk assessments (Sarra, Mikrad, & Sunanto, 2022). The necessity to cultivate a favorable and accountable corporate image, especially amid rising environmental consciousness, compels banks to adopt green banking practices irrespective of their internal risk assessments.

Stakeholder Theory reinforces this perspective by highlighting that banks must address the expectations and needs of various stakeholders who increasingly emphasize sustainability. These stakeholders apply pressure on banks to integrate environmental issues into their operations, frequently perceiving such efforts as indicative of long-term strategic alignment and ethical obligation (Citraningtyas, Widagdo, & Ika, 2024). Consequently, banks may emphasize stakeholder satisfaction and reputational enhancement over internal risk evaluations when making decisions about green banking. This is in line with the findings of Furqan & Sutrisno (2024) which found that risk profile does not affect green banking.

Good Corporate Governance and Green Banking

The larger the size of the board of commissioners, the greater the disclosure of green banking as a form of stakeholder responsibility to the community (Ahmar et al., 2024). Good corporate governance (GCG) does not have an influence on green banking, which may be due to the fact that the implementation of GCG is more focused on aspects of transparency, accountability, and internal control of the company in general, without specifically promoting environmental initiatives such as green banking. Legitimacy Theory elucidates this gap. Although companies frequently implement governance structures to uphold their legitimacy with financial and legal entities, this legitimacy does not invariably encompass environmental or sustainability legitimacy unless influenced by particular external pressures or strategic commitments directing that emphasis (Sarra, Mikrad, & Sunanto, 2022). Although GCG is important for the continuity and integrity of the company, in practice it does not necessarily reflect a commitment to environmental sustainability if not supported by a strategic vision or specific policies related to green banking. In other words, the existence of GCG does not automatically encourage the implementation of green banking practices. This is in line with the research conducted by Citraningtyas et al (2024), which did not find any influence of good corporate governance on green banking.

Earnings and Green Banking

Profitability (earning) measured by Return on Assets (ROA) has a negative impact on green banking because short-term financial performance like ROA does not always serve as the basis for long-term sustainable strategic decision-making. Banks with high ROA do not necessarily have an orientation towards green investments, because green banking is more driven by a commitment to social and environmental responsibility, as well as compliance with regulations, rather than solely by profit. From the perspective of Stakeholder Theory, green banking is primarily driven by the need to meet the expectations of key external stakeholders rather than by internal financial metrics. Banks that are highly profitable may feel less pressure to shift toward green initiatives unless these stakeholders explicitly demand such action (Citraningtyas, Widagdo, & Ika, 2024). In many cases, unless profitability aligns with stakeholder interests in sustainability, banks may prioritize traditional lending and investment activities that offer faster or more certain returns. Additionally, the implementation of green banking is often considered a long-term investment that may not immediately have a positive impact on profitability, so banks with high ROA might still be cautious in allocating funds for green initiatives. This is in line with the research conducted by Ahmar et al. (2024), which did not find any influence of ROA on green banking.

Capital and Green Banking

Capital measured by the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) has an influence on green banking because CAR reflects the bank's ability to bear risks and support financing expansion, including financing oriented towards the environment. Banks with a high CAR have sufficient capital reserves to allocate funds to green projects that may carry higher risks and longer payback periods. With a strong capital position, banks tend to be more flexible and confident in adopting green banking initiatives as part of their sustainable business strategy, while also meeting regulatory demands and stakeholder expectations for the bank's active role in supporting environmentally conscious development. Thus, CAR not only provides the financial foundation for green investments but also enables banks to navigate the legitimacy pressures and stakeholder demands that are increasingly shaping the modern banking landscape (Sarraf, Mikrad, & Sunanto, 2022). In line with the research findings of Citraningtyas et al., (2024) which found the influence of CAR on green banking. The results explain that with high capital, the bank has sufficient funds to implement green banking practices.

Conclusion

The research findings indicate that risk profile and earnings negatively affect green banking, whereas good corporate governance has no impact, and capital positively affects green banking practices, which has important theoretical implications. Based on legitimacy theory, these findings indicate that green banking practices are undertaken by banks not due to internal conditions, but rather to gain social legitimacy by demonstrating a commitment to environmental issues that are of public concern. Within the framework of stakeholder theory, these results indicate that the bank's decision to implement green banking is more influenced by external pressures from stakeholders such as regulators, investors, and the public, who demand active involvement in sustainability issues.

Meanwhile, the finding that CAR influences green banking aligns with compliance theory, where banks with strong capital have a greater ability to meet regulations or government policies related to sustainable finance. Thus, the implementation of green banking tends to be carried out as a response to external and regulatory demands, rather than purely internal considerations.

Recommendations

This research is inevitably constrained by several issues that may be resolved through future research; the suggestions made in this research may help in future research. Suggestions for this research are:

Subsequent research can consider other variables as additional factors of green banking, such as gender diversity. Additionally, crosscountry comparisons or longitudinal analyses can be implemented into further research.

Additionally, the research period could also select years following the Covid-19 pandemic to obtain stable data.

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